

Pointwise weighted approximation of functions with inner singularities by combinations of Bernstein operators

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Abstract.

We introduce another new type of combinations of Bernstein operators in this paper, which can be used to approximate the functions with inner singularities. The direct and inverse results of the weighted approximation of this new type combinations are obtained.

Keywords: Combinations of Bernstein polynomials; Functions with inner singularities; Weighted approximation; Direct and inverse results.

1 Introduction

The set of all continuous functions, defined on the interval I , is denoted by $C(I)$. For any $f \in C([0, 1])$, the corresponding *Bernstein operators* are defined as follows:

$$B_n(f, x) := \sum_{k=0}^n f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) p_{n,k}(x),$$

Where

$$p_{n,k}(x) := \binom{n}{k} x^k (1-x)^{n-k}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

Approximation properties of Bernstein operators have been studied very well (see [2], [3], [5]-[8], [12]-[14], for example). In order to approximate the functions with singularities, Della Vecchia et al. [3] and Yu-Zhao [12] introduced some kinds of modified Bernstein operators. Throughout the paper, C denotes a positive constant independent of n and x , which may be different in different cases.

Let $\bar{w}(x) = |x - \xi|^\alpha$, $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha > 0$ and $C_{\bar{w}} := \{f \in C([0, 1] \setminus \xi) : \lim_{x \rightarrow \xi} (\bar{w}f)(x) = 0\}$.

The norm in $C_{\bar{w}}$ is defined as $\|f\|_{C_{\bar{w}}} := \|\bar{w}f\| = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq 1} |(\bar{w}f)(x)|$. Define

$$W_{\bar{w}, \lambda}^r := \{f \in C_{\bar{w}} : f^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((0, 1)), \|\bar{w}\varphi^{\lambda} f^{(r)}\| < \infty\}.$$

For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, define the *weighted modulus of smoothness* by

$$\omega_{\varphi^{\lambda}}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}} := \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \{\|\bar{w}\Delta_{h\varphi^{\lambda}}^r f\|_{[16h^2, 1-16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\overrightarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[0, 16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[1-16h^2, 1]}\},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f\left(x + \left(\frac{r}{2} - k\right)h\varphi^\lambda(x)\right), \\ \vec{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (r - k)h), \\ \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x - kh),\end{aligned}$$

and $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$. The *weighted K-function* is given by

$$K_{r,\varphi^\lambda}(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} := \inf_g \{ \|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + t^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\| : g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r \}.$$

It was shown in [5] that $K_{r,\varphi^\lambda}(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} \sim \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}}$. On the other hand, since the *Bernstein polynomials* cannot be used for the investigation of higher orders of smoothness, Butzer [1] introduced the *combinations of Bernstein polynomials* which have higher orders of approximation. Ditzian and Totik [5] extended this method of combinations and defined the following combinations of Bernstein operators:

$$B_{n,r}(f, x) := \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) B_{n_i}(f, x).$$

with the conditions

- (a) $n = n_0 < n_1 < \dots < n_{r-1} \leq Cn$,
- (b) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| \leq C$, (c) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) = 1$,
- (d) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)n_i^{-k} = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, r-1$.

2 The main results

For any positive integer r , we consider the determinant

$$A_r := \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 2r+1 & 2r+2 & 2r+3 & \dots & 4r+1 \\ (2r)(2r+1) & (2r+1)(2r+2) & (2r+2)(2r+3) & \dots & (4r)(4r+1) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ 2 \dots (2r+1) & 3 \dots (2r+2) & 4 \dots (2r+3) & \dots & (2r+2) \dots (4r+1) \end{vmatrix}.$$

We obtain $A_r = \prod_{j=2}^{2r} j!$. Thus, there is a unique solution for the system of nonhomogeneous linear equations:

$$\begin{cases} a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_{2r+1} = 1, \\ (2r+1)a_1 + (2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0, \\ (2r+1)(2r)a_1 + (2r+1)(2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (4r)(4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0, \\ \vdots \\ (2r+1)!a_1 + 3 \dots (2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (2r+2) \dots (4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Let

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} a_1 x^{2r+1} + a_2 x^{2r+2} + \dots + a_{2r+1} x^{4r+1}, & 0 < x < 1, \\ 0, & x \leq 0, \\ 1, & x = 1. \end{cases}$$

with the coefficients $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{2r+1}$ satisfying (2.1). From (2.1), we see that $\psi(x) \in C^{(2r)}(-\infty, +\infty)$, $0 \leq \psi(x) \leq 1$ for $0 \leq x \leq 1$. Moreover, it holds that $\psi(1) = 1$, $\psi^{(i)}(0) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, 2r$ and $\psi^{(i)}(1) = 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2r$.

Let

$$H(f, x) := \sum_{i=1}^{r+1} f(x_i)l_i(x),$$

and

$$l_i(x) := \frac{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x - x_j)}{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x_i - x_j)}, \quad x_i = \frac{[n\xi - ((r-1)/2 + i)]}{n}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r+1.$$

Further, let

$$x'_1 = \frac{[n\xi - 2\sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_2 = \frac{[n\xi - \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_3 = \frac{[n\xi + \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_4 = \frac{[n\xi + 2\sqrt{n}]}{n},$$

and

$$\bar{\psi}_1(x) = \psi\left(\frac{x - x'_1}{x'_2 - x'_1}\right), \quad \bar{\psi}_2(x) = \psi\left(\frac{x - x'_3}{x'_4 - x'_3}\right).$$

Set

$$\bar{F}_n(f, x) := \bar{F}_n(x) = f(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_1(x) + \bar{\psi}_2(x)) + \bar{\psi}_1(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_2(x))H(x).$$

We have

$$\bar{F}_n(f, x) = \begin{cases} f(x), & x \in [0, x_{r-5/2}] \cup [x_{r+3/2}, 1], \\ f(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_1(x)) + \bar{\psi}_1(x)H(x), & x \in [x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}], \\ H(x), & x \in [x_{r-3/2}, x_{r+1/2}], \\ H(x)(1 - \bar{\psi}_2(x)) + \bar{\psi}_2(x)f(x), & x \in [x_{r+1/2}, x_{r+3/2}]. \end{cases}$$

Obviously, $\bar{F}_n(f, x)$ is linear, reproduces polynomials of degree r , and $\bar{F}_n(f, x) \in C^{(2r)}([0, 1])$, provided that $f \in C^{(2r)}([0, 1])$. Now, we can define our new combinations of Bernstein operators as follows:

$$\bar{B}_{n,r}(f, x) := B_{n,r}(\bar{F}_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)B_{n_i}(\bar{F}_n, x), \quad (2.2)$$

where $C_i(n)$ satisfy the conditions (a)-(d). Our main result is the following:

Theorem 1. For $f \in C_{\bar{\omega}}$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha > 0$, $0 < \alpha_0 < r$, we have

$$\bar{\omega}(x)|f(x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(f, x)| = O((n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\varphi^{-\lambda}(x)\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}) \iff \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{\omega}} = O(t^{\alpha_0}).$$

3 Lemmas

Lemma 1.([3]) If $\gamma \in R$, then

$$\sum_{k=0}^n p_{n,k}(x)|k - nx|^\gamma \leq Cn^{\frac{\gamma}{2}}\varphi^\gamma(x). \quad (3.1)$$

Lemma 2.([3]) Let $A_n(x) := \bar{\omega}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x)$. Then $A_n(x) \leq Cn^{-\alpha/2}$ for $0 < \xi < 1$ and $\alpha > 0$.

Lemma 3. For $0 < \xi < 1$, $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k-nx|^\beta p_{n,k}(x) \leq Cn^{(\beta-\alpha/2)} \varphi^\beta(x). \tag{3.2}$$

Proof. By lemma 2, we have

$$\bar{w}(x)^{\frac{1}{2n}} (\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x))^{\frac{2n-1}{2n}} \left(\sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k-nx|^{2n\beta} p_{n,k}(x) \right)^{\frac{1}{2n}} \leq Cn^{(\beta-\alpha/2)} \varphi^\beta(x).$$

Lemma 4. For any $\alpha > 0$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we have

$$\|\bar{w} \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f)\| \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|. \tag{3.3}$$

Proof. We first prove $x \in [0, \frac{1}{n}]$ (The same as $x \in (1 - \frac{1}{n}, 1]$), now

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \frac{n_i!}{(n_i-r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} |C_i(n) \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} |C_i(n) \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,0}(x) \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{n_i-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,n_i-r}(x) \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-r-1} \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\ &:= H_1 + H_2 + H_3. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \left(\sum_{j=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{r-j}{n_i})| + |\bar{F}_n(0)| \right) p_{n_i-r,0}(x) \\ &\leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} \left(\frac{n_i|x-\xi|}{r-j-n_i\xi} \right)^\alpha (1-x)^{n_i-r} \\ &\leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} (n_i|x-\xi|)^\alpha (1-x)^{n_i-r} \\ &\leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can get $H_2 \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|$, and $H_3 \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|$.

When $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}]$, according to [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \\ &= |\bar{w}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(\bar{F}_n, x)| \\ &= \bar{w}(x)(\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)|n_i^j \sum_{k/n_i \in A} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ &\quad + \bar{w}(x)(\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)|n_i^j \sum_{x'_2 \leq k/n_i \leq x'_3} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j H(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ &:= \sigma_1 + \sigma_2. \end{aligned}$$

Where $A := [0, x'_2] \cup [x'_3, 1]$, H is a linear function. If $\frac{k}{n_i} \in A$, when $\frac{\bar{w}(x)}{\bar{w}(\frac{k}{n_i})} \leq C(1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k - n_i x|^\alpha)$, we have $|k - n_i x| \geq \frac{\sqrt{n_i}}{2}$, also $Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{[(r-j)/2]}$, and $(\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} Q_j(x, n_i)n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{r+j/2}$.

By (3.1), then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &\leq C\varphi^{2r}(x)\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |C_i(n)|(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{r+j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ &\leq C\varphi^{2r}(x)\|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |C_i(n)|(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{r+j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} [1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k - n_i x|^\alpha]|x - \frac{k}{n_i}|^j p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ &:= I_1 + I_2. \end{aligned}$$

By a simple calculation, we have $I_1 \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|$. By (3.1), then

$$I_2 \leq C\|\bar{w}f\|\varphi^{2r}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |C_i(n)|n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}+j} (\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |k - n_i x|^{\alpha+j} p_{n_i,k}(x) \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

We note that $|H(\frac{k}{n_i})| \leq \max(|H(x'_1)|, |H(x'_4)|) := H(a)$.

If $x \in [x'_1, x'_4]$, we have $\bar{w}(x) \leq \bar{w}(a)$. So, if $x \in [x'_1, x'_4]$, then

$$\sigma_2 \leq Cn^r \bar{w}(a)H(a) \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

If $x \notin [x'_1, x'_4]$, then $\bar{w}(a) > n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}$, by lemma 3, we have

$$\sigma_2 \leq C\bar{w}(a)H(a)\varphi^{-2r}(x)\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} C_i(n)n_i^{r+\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sum_{x'_2 \leq k/n_i \leq x'_3} p_{n_i,k}(x) \leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

It follows from combining the above inequalities that the lemma is proved. \square

Lemma 5. ([15]) If $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, $\alpha > 0$, then

$$\int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r\beta}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \leq Ch^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-\beta)}(x). \quad (3.4)$$

Lemma 6. For any $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $f \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{F}_n^{(r)}\| \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\|. \quad (3.5)$$

Proof. We first prove $x \in [x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]$ (The same as the others), we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)\bar{F}_n^{(r)}(x)| &\leq |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)f^{(r)}(x)| + |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)(f(x) - \bar{F}_n(x))^{(r)}| \\ &:= I_1 + I_2. \end{aligned}$$

Obviously

$$I_1 \leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

For I_2 , we have

$$I_2 = \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|(f(x) - \bar{F}_n(x))^{(r)}| = \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^r n^{\frac{i}{2}} |(f(x) - \bar{F}_n(x))^{(r-i)}|.$$

By [5], we have

$$|(f(x) - \bar{F}_n(x))^{(r-i)}|_{[x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]} \leq C(n^{(r-i)/2} \|f - H\|_{[x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]} + n^{-i/2} \|f^{(r)}\|_{[x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]}).$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|f - H\|_{[x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]} + C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|f^{(r)}\|_{[x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]} \\ &:= T_1 + T_2. \end{aligned}$$

By Taylor expansion, we have

$$f(x_i) = \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{(x_i - x)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds, \quad (3.6)$$

It follows from (3.6) and the identities

$$\sum_{i=1}^r x_i^v l_i(x) = Cx^v, \quad v = 0, 1, \dots, r.$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} H(f, x) &= \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{u=0}^r \frac{(x_i - x)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) l_i(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds \\ &= f(x) + \sum_{u=1}^r f^{(u)}(x) \left(\sum_{v=0}^u C_u^v (-x)^{u-v} \sum_{i=1}^r x_i^v l_i(x) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|f(x) - H(f, x)| = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$. It follows from $\frac{|x_i - s|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(s)} \leq \frac{|x_i - x|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(x)}$, s between x_i and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|f(x) - H(f, x)| &= C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} |f^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - x)^{r-1} \int_x^{x_i} \varphi^{-r\lambda}(s) ds \\ &\leq \frac{C}{n^{r/2}} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$I_2 \leq C \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

Then, the lemma is proved. \square

Lemma 7. For any $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x)|g(x) - H(g, x)| \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\|. \quad (3.7)$$

Proof. According to the lemma 6, we only give a simple proof.

$$\bar{w}(x)|g(x) - H(g, x)| = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} g^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [x_{r-5/2}, x_{r-3/2}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$. It follows from $\frac{|x_i-s|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(s)} \leq \frac{|x_i-x|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(x)}$, s between x_i and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - H(g, x)| &\leq C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{x_i} (x_i - s)^{r-1} |g^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - x)^{r-1} \int_x^{x_i} \varphi^{-r\lambda}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\varphi^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - x)^{r-1} \int_x^{x_i} \varphi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)} \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - x)^{r-1} \int_x^{x_i} \varphi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\|. \square \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 8. If $r \in N$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $f \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \quad (3.8)$$

Proof. It follows from $\frac{|t-u|}{\bar{w}(u)} \leq \frac{|t-x|}{\bar{w}(x)}$, u between t and x , let $t = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n_i^r |\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| &= n_i^r \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq C n_i^r \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}\| \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \bar{w}^{-1}(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r) \\ &\quad \varphi^{-r\lambda}(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &= C n_i^r \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}\| \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \frac{(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)}{\bar{w}(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)} \\ &\quad \varphi^{-r\lambda}(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\quad \frac{(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)}{(x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)} \\ &\leq C n_i^r \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}\| \frac{x}{\bar{w}(x)} \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{1}{2n_i}}^{\frac{1}{2n_i}} (x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)^{-(\frac{r\lambda}{2}+1)} \\ &\quad [1 - (x + \frac{rh}{2} + u_1 + \cdots + u_r)]^{-\frac{r\lambda}{2}} du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq C \bar{w}^{-1}(x) \varphi^{-r\lambda}(x) \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}\| \\ &\leq C \bar{w}^{-1}(x) \varphi^{-r\lambda}(x) \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

By [5], we have

$$\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \frac{n_i!}{(n_i - r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} C_i(n) \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i}) p_{n_i-r,k}(x).$$

Obviously

$$|\bar{w}(x) \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \leq C \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \square$$

Lemma 9. If $r \in N$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x) \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \leq C n^{r/2} \{max\{n^{r(1-\lambda)/2}, \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}\}\} \|\bar{w} f\|. \quad (3.9)$$

Proof. Case 1. If $0 \leq \varphi(x) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by (3.3), we have

$$|\bar{w}(x) \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \leq C n^{-r\lambda/2} |\bar{w}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \leq C n^{r(1-\lambda/2)} \|\bar{w} f\|.$$

Case 2. If $\varphi(x) > \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| &= |B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(\bar{F}_n, x)| \\ &\leq (\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |Q_j(x, n_i) C_i(n)| n_i^j \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{[(2r-j)/2]}, \text{ and } (\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} Q_j(x, n_i) n_i^j \leq C (n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{r+j/2}.$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f, x)| \\
 \leq & C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r(\lambda+2)}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-2}\sum_{j=0}^r|C_i(n)|\left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2}\sum_{k=0}^{n_i}\left|(x-\frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 = & C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r(\lambda+2)}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-2}\sum_{j=0}^r|C_i(n)|\left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2}\sum_{k/n_i\in A}\left|(x-\frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j\bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 & +C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{r(\lambda+2)}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-2}\sum_{j=0}^r|C_i(n)|\left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2}\sum_{x'_2\leq k/n_i\leq x'_3}\left|(x-\frac{k}{n_i}\right)^jH\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 := & \sigma_1 + \sigma_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $A := [0, x'_2] \cup [x'_3, 1]$. According to lemma 3, we can easily get $\sigma_1 \leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}}\varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x)\|\bar{w}f\|$, and $\sigma_2 \leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}}\varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x)\|\bar{w}f\|$. By bringing these facts together, the lemma is proved. \square

4 Proof of Theorem

The direct theorem

We know

$$\bar{F}_n(t) = \bar{F}_n(x) + \bar{F}'_n(t)(t-x) + \dots + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} \bar{F}_n^{(r)}(u) du, \tag{4.1}$$

$$B_{n,r-1}((\cdot-x)^k, x) = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, r-1. \tag{4.2}$$

According to the definition of $W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, for any $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, we have $\bar{B}_{n,r-1}(g, x) = B_{n,r-1}(\bar{G}_n(g), x)$ and $\bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(\bar{G}_n, x)| = \bar{w}(x)|B_{n,r-1}(R_r(\bar{G}_n, t, x), x)|$, thereof $R_r(\bar{G}_n, t, x) = \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} \bar{G}_n^{(r)}(u) du$.

It follows from $\frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(u)} \leq \frac{|t-x|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(x)}$, u between t and x , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(\bar{G}_n, x)| & \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\|\bar{w}(x)B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}(u)\varphi^{r\lambda}(u)} du, x\right) \\
 & \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\|\bar{w}(x)\left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(u)} |du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
 & \quad \left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}^2(u)} du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

also

$$\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(u)} du \leq C\frac{|t-x|^r}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)}, \quad \int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\bar{w}^2(u)} du \leq \frac{|t-x|^r}{\bar{w}^2(x)}. \tag{4.4}$$

By (3.1), (4.3) and (4.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(\bar{G}_n, x)| & \leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\|\varphi^{-r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}(|t-x|^r, x) \\
 & \leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}}\frac{\varphi^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\| \\
 & \leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}}\frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\| \\
 & = C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r\|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\|.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

By (3.7) and (4.5), when $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(g, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{G}_n(g, x)| + \bar{w}(x)|\bar{G}_n(g, x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(g, x)| \\ &\leq \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - H(g, x)|_{[x_1, x_4]} + C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}\bar{G}_n^{(r)}\| \\ &\leq C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we choose proper $g \in W_{\bar{w},\lambda}^r$, by (4.6), then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|f(x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(f, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x)|f(x) - g(x)| + \bar{w}(x)|\bar{B}_{n,r-1}(f - g, x)| + \bar{w}(x)|g(x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(g, x)| \\ &\leq C(\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\|) \\ &\leq C\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)})_{\bar{w}}. \square \end{aligned}$$

The inverse theorem

We define the weighted main-part modulus for $D = R_+$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(C, f, t)_{\bar{w}} &= \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \|\bar{w}\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)}, \\ \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(1, f, t)_{\bar{w}} &= \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}}. \end{aligned}$$

where $C > 2^{1/\beta(0)-1}$, $\beta(0) > 0$, and h^* is given by

$$h^* = \begin{cases} (Ar)^{1/1-\beta(0)}h^{1/1-\beta(0)}, & 0 \leq \beta(0) < 1, \\ 0, & \beta(0) \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

The main-part K -functional is given by

$$H_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} = \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \inf_g \{ \|\bar{w}(f - g)\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)} + t^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)}, g^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((Ch^*, \infty)) \}.$$

By [5], we have

$$C^{-1}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \tau)_{\bar{w}}}{\tau} d\tau, \quad (4.7)$$

$$C^{-1}H_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} \leq \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}} \leq CH_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}}. \quad (4.8)$$

Proof. Let $\delta > 0$, by (4.8), we choose proper g so that

$$\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| \leq C\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}}, \quad \|\bar{w}\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\| \leq C\delta^{-r}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}}. \quad (4.9)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| &\leq |\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r(f(x) - \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(f, x))| + |\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(f - g, x)| \\ &\quad + |\bar{w}(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r \bar{B}_{n,r-1}(g, x)| \\ &\leq \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j (n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x + (\frac{r}{2} - j)h\varphi^\lambda(x)))^{\alpha_0} \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(f - g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &:= J_1 + J_2 + J_3. \end{aligned}$$

Obviously

$$J_1 \leq C(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}. \tag{4.10}$$

By (3.3) and (4.9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq Cn^r \|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq Cn^r h^r \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \\ &\leq Cn^r h^r \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

By (3.9) we let $\lambda = 1$, and (3.4) as well as (4.9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x) \|\bar{w}(f-g)\| \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x) \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

By (3.8) and (4.9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_3 &\leq C \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \bar{w}(x) \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \bar{w}^{-1}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) \varphi^{-r\lambda}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq Ch^r \|\bar{w} \varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \\ &\leq Ch^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

Now, by (4.10), (4.11), (4.12) and (4.13), we get

$$|\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| \leq C \{ (n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0} + h^r (n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{-r} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w} + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w} \}.$$

When $n \geq 2$, we have

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x) \leq \sqrt{2} n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x),$$

Choosing proper $x, n \in N$, so that

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) \leq \delta < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x),$$

Therefore

$$|\bar{w}(x) \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| \leq C \{ \delta^{\alpha_0} + h^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta) \bar{w} \}.$$

By Borens-Lorentz lemma, we get

$$\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t) \bar{w} \leq Ct^{\alpha_0}. \tag{4.14}$$

So, by (4.14), we get

$$\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t) \bar{w} \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \tau) \bar{w}}{\tau} d\tau = C \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha_0-1} d\tau = Ct^{\alpha_0}. \square$$

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References

- [1] P.L. Butzer, Linear combinations of Bernstein polynomials, *Canad. J. Math.* 5 (1953), pp. 559-567.
- [2] H. Berens and G. Lorentz, Inverse theorems for Bernstein polynomials, *Indiana Univ. Math. J.* 21 (1972), pp. 693-708.
- [3] D. Della Vechhia, G. Mastroianni and J. Szabados, Weighted approximation of functions with endpoint and inner singularities by Bernstein operators, *Acta Math. Hungar.* 103 (2004), pp. 19-41.
- [4] Z. Ditzian, A global inverse theorem for combinations of Bernstein polynomials, *J. Approx. Theory* 26 (1979), pp. 277-292.
- [5] Z. Ditzian and V. Totik, *Moduli of Smoothness*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, New York (1987).
- [6] S.S. Guo, C.X. Li and X.W. Liu, Pointwise approximation for linear combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 107 (2000), pp. 109-120.
- [7] S.S. Guo, H. Tong and G. Zhang, Pointwise weighted approximation by Bernstein operators, *Acta Math. Hungar.* 101 (2003), pp. 293-311.
- [8] G.G. Lorentz, *Bernstein Polynomial*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto (1953).
- [9] L.S. Xie, Pointwise simultaneous approximation by combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 137 (2005), pp. 1-21.
- [10] L.S. Xie, The saturation class for linear combinations of Bernstein operators, *Arch. Math.* 91 (2008), pp. 86-96.
- [11] D.S. Yu, Weighted approximation of functions with singularities by combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Applied Mathematics and Computation.* 206(2008), pp.906-918.
- [12] D.S. Yu and D.J. Zhao, Approximation of functions with singularities by truncated Bernstein operators, *Southeast Bull. Math.* 30 (2006), pp. 1178-1189.
- [13] D.X. Zhou, Rate of convergence for Bernstein operators with Jacobi weights, *Acta Math. Sinica* 35 (1992), pp. 331-338.
- [14] D.X. Zhou, On smoothness characterized by Bernstein type operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 81 (1994), pp. 303-315.
- [15] J.J. Zhang, Z.B. Xu, Direct and inverse approximation theorems with Jacobi weight for combinations and higher derivatives of Baskakov operators (in Chinese), *Journal of systems science and mathematical sciences.* 2008 28 (1), pp. 30-39.